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Research Article

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice Regarding Medication Use During Pregnancy: Impact of a Pharmaceutical Care Intervention in a Hospital-Based Study

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ABSTRACT

Safe medication use during pregnancy is essential for maternal and fetal health. Inadequate awareness often leads to inappropriate self-medication and poor practices. This study aimed to assess the impact of a pharmaceutical care intervention on knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) regarding medication use during pregnancy. A hospital-based prospective interventional study was conducted over six months at a tertiary care hospital in Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka. One hundred pregnant women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) were screened; 50 with poor KAP scores were included and randomized into intervention (n=25) and control (n=25) groups. The intervention group received patient information leaflets (PIL) and pharmacist counseling, while the control group received standard care. Pre- and post-intervention KAP scores were assessed using a validated questionnaire. Results showed significant improvement in the intervention group post-intervention: misconceptions about medication safety reduced from 68% to 24% ($p<0.001$), positive attitudes toward consulting physicians and pharmacists increased from 16% to 80% ($p<0.001$), and safe practices such as avoiding self-medication improved from 76% to 12% ($p<0.001$). No significant changes were observed in the control group. This study concludes that structured pharmacist-led educational interventions significantly improve knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding medication use during pregnancy. Incorporating pharmaceutical care into antenatal programs can enhance safe medication practices and maternal outcomes.

INTRODUCTION

Medication use during pregnancy is a matter of critical importance, as inappropriate practices can lead to adverse maternal and fetal outcomes.

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Pregnant women often overestimate the teratogenic risk of drugs, resulting in reluctance to take prescribed medicines, or conversely may use non-prescribed drugs due to poor awareness.¹ Safe prescribing during pregnancy therefore requires not only clinical judgment but also patient education to correct misconceptions.

Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) studies provide insights into existing gaps, misconceptions, and behaviors regarding drug use.² They also help in designing educational interventions aimed at improving rational drug use. Previous studies across India and globally have reported variable knowledge levels among pregnant women, with significant proportions relying on self-medication.^{3,4}

Pharmaceutical care interventions by clinical pharmacists, including structured counseling and patient information leaflets (PILs), have been shown to improve knowledge and adherence in chronic diseases.⁵ However, limited research exists on their role in improving KAP regarding medication use during pregnancy in the Indian setting.

Hence, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the impact of a pharmaceutical care intervention on KAP regarding medication use among pregnant women with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

A hospital-based, prospective interventional study was conducted for six months at a tertiary care hospital in Dakshina Kannada, Karnataka.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee (Ref No: SIEC/SIMS & RC/53/03/2024). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Participants

Pregnant women aged ≥ 18 years, diagnosed with GDM, were eligible. Women with psychiatric illness, pre-existing diabetes, or unwilling to consent were excluded.

Sample Size and Grouping

Out of 100 screened, 50 with poor baseline KAP scores were included. They were divided equally into control (n=25) and intervention (n=25) groups.

Intervention

The intervention group received structured pharmacist counseling and a patient information leaflet (PIL) focusing on safe medication practices in pregnancy. The control group received routine care.

Data Collection Tool

A validated KAP questionnaire was used. Scores ≥ 6 indicated good KAP, while < 3 indicated poor KAP.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel. Pre- and post-intervention scores were compared using Chi-square and unpaired t-tests. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

Baseline KAP Scores: Out of 100 women screened, 50 had good KAP and were excluded; 50 with poor KAP were randomized equally.

Table 1: Distribution of subject based on KAP score

KAP	N=100
GOOD KAP SCORE	50
POOR KAP SCORE	50

Knowledge: Before intervention, 68% of women believed any medication could be used at any stage of pregnancy. This reduced to 24% post-intervention ($p<0.001$). Understanding about risks of non-prescribed medication use improved from 32% to 76%.

Table 2. Knowledge of study participants on medication use during pregnancy

Questions	Response	Intervention group n=25		Control group n=25		P value
		PRE	POST	PRE	POST	
Any medication can be used at any stage of pregnancy	Yes	17(68%)	6(24%)	18(72%)	17(68%)	<0.00001
	No	8(32%)	19(76%)	7(28%)	8(32%)	
Some medications may be more suitable to be used during some stage of pregnancy	Yes	4(16%)	21(84%)	5(20%)	8(32%)	<0.00001
	No	21(84%)	4(16%)	20(80%)	17(68%)	
A non-prescribed medication can be used during pregnancy	Yes	17(68%)	6(24%)	16(64%)	14(56%)	<0.00001
	No	8(32%)	19(76%)	9(36%)	11(44%)	
Wrong drug choice can affect the formation of the fetus and health of the mother	Yes	13(52%)	19(76%)	7(28%)	7(28%)	<0.00001
	No	12(48%)	6(24%)	18(72%)	18(72%)	
The pharmacist should Provide all necessary information and advice regarding the medication before using it	Yes	4(16%)	21(84%)	5(20%)	6(24%)	<0.00001
	No	22(88%)	4(16%)	20(80%)	19(76%)	
It is safe to take common medications and over the counter drugs without the physician or pharmacist's advice	Yes	21(84%)	3(12%)	22(88%)	19(76%)	<0.000056
	No	4(16%)	22(88%)	3(12%)	6(24%)	

Attitude

($p < 0.001$). Verification of medication safety before use increased from 16% to 80%.

Self-medication without physician consultation decreased from 88% to 12% post-intervention

Table 3. Attitude of study participants on medication use during pregnancy

QUESTIONS	RESPONSE	INTERVENTION GROUP n=25 (%)		CONTROL GROUP n=25 (%)		P value
		PRE	POST	PRE	POST	
Take medication without physician's prescription	Yes	22(88%)	3(12%)	20 (80%)	20(80%)	<0.00001
	No	3(12%)	22(88%)	5 (20%)	5(20%)	
Verify the safety of medication before taking them	Yes	4(16%)	20(80%)	6 (24%)	10(40%)	<0.00001
	No	21(84%)	5(20%)	19(76%)	15(60%)	
All medications are the same and can be used in pregnant women	Yes	18(72%)	5(20%)	15(60%)	13(60%)	<0.001411
	No	7(28%)	20(80%)	10(40%)	12(48%)	
Avoid medications because of the risk to my baby	Yes	16(64%)	5(20%)	17(68%)	14(56%)	<0.000852
	No	9(36%)	20(80%)	8(32%)	11(44%)	
There should be no restriction of drugs during pregnancy because the baby needs it.	Yes	21(84%)	23(92%)	18(72%)	18(72%)	<0.00001
	No	4(16%)	2(8%)	7(28%)	7(28%)	
It is better to take natural remedies during pregnancy	Yes	20(80%)	3(12%)	19(76%)	16(64%)	<0.00001
	No	5(20%)	22(88%)	6(24%)	9(36%)	

Practice

Routine use of OTC medications without consultation decreased from 84% to 12%

(p<0.001). Consulting pharmacists for advice improved from 24% to 80%.

Table 4. Practice of study participants on medication use during pregnancy

QUESTION	RESPONSE	INTERVENTION GROUP n=25 (%)		CONTROL GROUP n=25 (%)		P value
		PRE	POST	PRE	POST	
Took routine medications without asking your doctor or pharmacist	YES	19(76%)	3(12%)	18(72%)	18(72%)	<0.00001
	NO	6(24%)	22(88%)	7(28%)	7(28%)	
Took over-the-counter drugs without asking your doctor or pharmacist	YES	21(84%)	3(12%)	20(80%)	19(76%)	<0.00001
	NO	3(12%)	22(88%)	5(20%)	6(24%)	
Saw your doctor to obtain a prescription before taking any medication	YES	5(20%)	20(80%)	6(24%)	6(24%)	<0.00001
	NO	20(80%)	5(20%)	19(76%)	19(76%)	
Asked about the drug to know if pregnant women could take it	YES	10(40%)	23(92%)	7(28%)	9(36%)	<0.00001
	NO	15(60%)	2(8%)	18(72%)	16(64%)	
Checked the leaflet of the drug you take to know if pregnant women could take it	YES	6(24%)	23(92%)	10(40%)	10(40%)	<0.00001
	NO	19(76%)	2(8%)	15(60%)	15(60%)	
Asked the pharmacist for advice regarding the safety of the medications you take during pregnancy	YES	6(24%)	20(80%)	7(28%)	10(40%)	<0.000056
	NO	19(76%)	5(20%)	18(72%)	15(60%)	

Pre- and post-intervention comparison of KAP in intervention group

Figure 5. Pre- and post-intervention comparison of KAP in intervention group

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that structured pharmaceutical care interventions significantly improve KAP regarding medication use in pregnancy. Misconceptions, such as believing all medications are safe during pregnancy or relying on natural remedies without consultation, were effectively corrected.

These results are consistent with earlier studies from Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, and India, where poor baseline knowledge and misconceptions were common, but education significantly improved awareness and practices.⁶

The study highlights the crucial role of pharmacists as part of antenatal care teams. Integrating pharmacist-led education during antenatal visits can help reduce unsafe practices, improve adherence, and ultimately prevent adverse outcomes.

Limitations include the small sample size, single-center design, and short follow-up. Larger multicenter studies are recommended to generalize findings.

CONCLUSION

Pharmaceutical care intervention significantly improved knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding medication use during pregnancy. Incorporating pharmacist counseling into routine antenatal care can enhance maternal safety and promote rational medication use.

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REFERENCES

1. Smedberg J, Brønstad I, Nilsen RM, et al. Medication use and drug-related problems among women at maternity wards—a cross-sectional study from two Norwegian hospitals. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2016;72(6):741-749.
2. Obi OC, Eze UI, Erah PO. Knowledge, attitude and practice of medication use among pregnant women in Nigeria. *Trop J Pharm Res.* 2018;17(3):455-462.

3. Zaki NM, Albarraq AA. Use, attitudes and knowledge of medications among pregnant women: a Saudi study. *Saudi Pharm J.* 2014;22(5):419-428.
4. Tan J, Zhang Y, Jiang Y, et al. Knowledge, attitude and practice survey on gestational diabetes mellitus among Chinese women. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth.* 2020;20:689.
5. Elnour AA, Mohammed M, Ibrahim MI. Impact of pharmaceutical care on health outcomes in patients with gestational diabetes mellitus. *Int J Clin Pharm.* 2008;30(6):845-853.
6. Shafaiyaz M, Aruna D, et al. Knowledge, attitude and practices regarding gestational diabetes mellitus among antenatal women in Chennai, India. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol.* 2019;8(5):1841-1847.

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